

PROCEDURE. Systematic observation of parental and child behavior in three social interaction situations.

Description

This procedure is part of *the Parents as Facilitators of Their Children's Friendships (PyM-Fa) program*. Before and after the *PyM as Facilitators training sessions*, parents are recorded in situations where their child plays with three other children: 10 minutes of structured play (for example, *The Game of the Goose*) (Situation 1: Structured Play) and another 10 to 15 minutes of free play, where the children can choose from various board games available to them (Situation 2: Free Play). In both situations, the child's behavior while playing with the other children and the parent's interaction with their child are observed and analyzed. At the end of these play sessions, each family member goes with their child to another room where the private interaction between the parent and child is recorded. During this recording, the parent provides feedback to the child about the play sessions with other children in which the child has just participated and which the parent has observed (Situation 3: Parent-Child Interaction). In this third situation, the interaction between the parent and their child is observed and analyzed. The three experimental situations are described in detail in the *observation protocol for parental and child behavior* (Documents: Structured Play_Measure; Free Play_Measure; Parent-Child Interaction_Measure, respectively). The main objective of the procedure is to evaluate the quality of the interaction between the parent and their child, and between the child and their peers.

, a coding system has been designed for parental interaction behavior with the child and for the child's interaction behavior with other children and with their family member (Documents: STRUCTURED PLAY_Measure-CodingSystem; FREE PLAY_Measure-CodingSystem; PARENT-CHILD INTERACTION_Measure-CodingSystem, respectively), and *the observations are noted in the corresponding record* (For each situation, between 2 and 4 versions of records or data sheets are offered: STRUCTURED PLAY_Measure-CodingSheet-1 and STRUCTURED PLAY_Measure-CodingSheet-2; FREE PLAY_Measure-CodingSheet-1 and FREE PLAY_Measure-CodingSheet-2; PARENT-CHILD INTERACTION_Measure-CodingSheet-1, PARENT-CHILD INTERACTION_Measure-CodingSheet-2v1, PARENT-CHILD INTERACTION_Measure-CodingSheet-2v2 and PARENT-CHILD INTERACTION_Measure-CodingSheet-3, respectively). For the first two situations, the behavior of the family member and the child is recorded every minute. Alternatively, a new entry is made each time a different behavior is observed in the child or the family member. For the third situation, the process is slightly more complex. First, the interaction between the family member and the child is transcribed. Second, the transcription is inserted into the protocol for recording parental behavior in interaction situations with their child (Document PARENT-CHILD INTERACTION_Measure-CodingSheet-2v1). The document prepared for coding subject 214216 is provided as an example (Document: PARENT-CHILD INTERACTION_Measure-CodingSheet-2v2). Third, each behavior is evaluated

according to the developed coding system (Document: PARENT-CHILD INTERACTION_Measure-CodingSystem). Coding is performed independently by four evaluators (PI, principal investigator, two other team members, etc.), who are randomly assigned to each child's transcript.

This procedure provides information to the process of promoting and verifying the integrity of the intervention, specifically regarding its application component. The before-and-after analysis of parental and child behavior reveals the degree to which participants —family members and children— have incorporated the mechanisms and behaviors addressed in the intervention program into their interactions. On the one hand, it allows for verification of the parents' integration of the teachings imparted in the program. *PyM-Fa* as facilitators in their interactions with their children. Furthermore, the analysis of the child's behavior through before-and-after recordings also allows observation of possible progress in the quality of interaction with peers of the children participating in the friendship learning sessions, and the application of strategies worked on in those sessions.

Source : Observers (Researchers).